

Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) Tools in Education and Teachers' Preparation Strategies in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT: *Recently, there has been an increase in studies on the integration of artificial intelligence in educational service delivery. Many scholars believe that the role of teachers will change. They need to be prepared for AI-powered education. For this investigation, a descriptive survey research design was adopted. The principals and teachers in the 274 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State formed the population. Using the stratified random sampling technique, a sample of 407 respondents (69 principals and 338 teachers) was drawn. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Data was collected with the aid of a questionnaire tagged, "Integration of Artificial Intelligence in Education and Teachers Preparation Strategies Questionnaire". The instrument, which has 16 items, was well validated by research experts, and using Cronbach's Alpha, the calculated reliability coefficient was 0.83, indicating that it was reliable. Mean, mean set, and standard deviation were used to analyse the research questions, while the z-test was used to test the hypotheses. Results of the study showed that AI can be used to improve learning outcomes by reducing teachers' workload, providing personalized education to learners, and enhancing accessibility of education. On the other hand, teachers appear not to be prepared for AI-enabled classrooms. They need Artificial Intelligence (AI) literacy and professional development. From the results of the study, a conclusion was drawn, and the researchers recommended, among others; that Artificial Intelligence (AI) awareness and competency should be increased among teachers through teachers' training courses and professional development programs.*

KEYWORDS: *Integration, Artificial Intelligence, Education, Teacher Preparation, and Public Secondary School.*

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INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence is an emerging technological domain capable of impacting every field of study, including education. It is one of the most important challenges facing this era, as it has become an integral part of our lives. Artificial intelligence has affected various disciplines, starting with simple computers and advancing to smartphones and robots [1]. Artificial intelligence is defined as a science that includes all the algorithms and theoretical and practical methods concerned with automating decision-making processes. The place of man, whether completely or partially, with the human body and ability to adapt, quote, and predict [2]. In simple terms, artificial intelligence (AI) may be described as the ability of machines or

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computers to think and act as human beings. It represents the efforts towards computerized systems to imitate the human mind and actions [3]. It is based on this premise that [4] defined artificial intelligence as the skillful imitation of human behaviour or mind by tools or programs.

Artificial intelligence, according to [4], could be defined from the following perspectives:

A) Thinking Humanly

1. The exciting new effort to make computers think.
2. Machines with minds, in the full and literal sense.
3. The automation of activities such as decision-making, problem-solving, learning, etc.

B) Acting Humanly

1. The art of creating machines that perform functions that require intelligence when performed by people.
2. The study of how computer communicate like a human (natural language, tone, context).

C) Thinking Rationally

1. The study of mental faculties through the use of computational models.
2. The study of the computations that make it possible to perceive, reason, and act.

D) Acting Rationally

1. Computational intelligence is the study of the design of intelligent agents.
2. AI is concerned with intelligent behaviour in artifacts.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a machine with some extent of human intelligence [6] and/or the intelligence of other life forms. It is a creation of human intelligence. Due to the various dimensions of the impact of AI, it has turned out to be a major area of investment by many countries today. According to [7], artificial intelligence is the new electricity of this age. It is seen by many as a powerful factor in ensuring economic development. This appears to be the major reason why investment in artificial intelligence broke a record in China with \$40 billion in 2017. According to [8], countries like China and North America are expected to increase their gross domestic product (GDP) by 26% and 15% respectively, by 2023, due to their investments in AI.

The in-depth development of AI, according to [9], will affect many situations, from the restructuring of the social order in the broadest sense to the education and administration processes in classes and schools. To [10], The whole world is going digital, where digital technologies and artificial intelligence (AI) are integrated in the management of businesses and education. Schools that are expected to adapt to the digital age and embed 21st-century skills in their curriculum are the main institutions that could be most affected by the development of AI. Educational institutions are therefore expected to integrate AI into their schools. Integration means incorporating, combining or joining two or more things, such as systems, processes, ideas, or organizations into a unified whole. It involves bringing together different components, functions, or perspectives to create a cohesive, harmonious, and often more effective or efficient entity.

Integrating AI in the educational system ensures equitable and inclusive access to education [5]. It provides marginalized people and communities, people with disabilities, refugees, those out of schools, and those living in isolated communities with access to appropriate learning opportunities. AI enhances collaborative learning. One of the most revolutionary aspects of computer-supported collaborative learning is found in situations where learners are not physically in the same location [5]. It provides students with variable choices of when and where they wish to study. AI systems could be used to monitor asynchronous discussion groups and discussions, and provide support for guiding learners' engagement and learning. AI, according to [11], could help teachers improve personalized education for their students. Research shows how effective individually tailored approaches can be presented with the support of AI techniques and intelligent learning environments.

Developments in the education sector in Nigeria recently are gradually directed towards the adoption of AI as an approach for tutors to be able to offer more effective services in schools. Integrating AI in secondary education can be approached through the following strategies:

1. Adaptive learning systems (ALS): Utilizing adaptive learning systems can help identify students' strengths, weaknesses, and learning preferences, offering personalized learning pathways, tools, and assessments [12].
2. AI-powered Tutoring systems: Adopting AI-powered tutoring systems can increase learner engagement and address deficiencies in learners' knowledge [13].
3. Virtual laboratories: Creating and utilizing virtual laboratories can provide students with hands-on experience and enhance their understanding of complex scientific concepts [14].
4. Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS): The use of ITS can be of great benefit to learners. It can enhance their engagement and, at the same time, address deficiencies in learners' knowledge [15].

The adaptation of AI in the school setting will enhance the exposure of tutors to machine learning in the new dispensation and smart manipulations during instructional delivery. It also helps tutor to apply age-appropriate hardware and software to ease their work at school. Several researchers, such as [16], [17], and [18], have posited that AI is capable of reducing the workload of teachers in schools. According to [15], this could be in the areas of teaching automation and evaluation, teacher administration, keeping learner attendance, an intelligent teaching system for special education, and recommending useful materials for pupils.

Artificial intelligence-powered classrooms and systems create a dual teacher situation, thus enabling the existence of a human teacher and a smart teaching device simultaneously in a classroom setting. According to [19], tutors and educators can deploy simple smart machines such as ChatGPT, Nerd AI, Ask AI, Gen AI, to generate ideas, solve problems, develop a lesson plan, and share ideas with learners and colleagues in a few seconds. The utilization of an AI device aligns with the activity-based approach of conducting classroom lessons.

Despite the benefits associated with the integration of AI in education service delivery. Several factors pose themselves as big challenges to the incorporation of AI in education, as a way to improve the equity and quality of learning, and effective and efficient preparation of students for work, and solving problems facing them. These challenges may be perceived from the following angles: teacher preparation/training, infrastructural development, curriculum review/development, policy formulation, and collaboration/partnership. This study focused more attention on examining teachers' preparation challenges for the incorporation of AI in educational service delivery in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. According to [12], a 2023 report by Oxford University Press found that whilst many teachers believed that AI would have a positive effect on education, only 23% of UK teachers felt prepared for a shift toward an AI-enabled classroom. There is an urgent call for the training of teachers on the use of AI in education.

The major challenge teachers may face is the lack of professional development programs and training. Acquiring the necessary skills and knowledge to integrate AI tools into their teaching practices effectively can be difficult without proper support and training. According to [20], performing a skill upgrade to be able to use the AI in school is vital for today's school teachers. It is an adjustment that tends to take the educator a step further by producing a re-modernised teacher to match the age of high-tech in education. Teachers need to be trained on how to use AI tools wisely. They need to understand their capabilities and limitations, and develop effective teaching strategies that leverage the potential of AI [14]. Supporting this view, [20] stated that training programs should focus on practical skills, enabling teachers to confidently integrate AI tools into their practices.

Preparing teachers for the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into their jobs requires a multi-dimensional approach. There is a need to enhance their AI literacy and competence. Teachers, according to [20], should be provided with foundational knowledge of AI, its applications, and implications for education. Teachers should be offered hands-on training on AI-powered platforms, resources, and tools in their subject areas. This, according to [14], will upgrade their skills and enhance their efficiency in the utilization of AI-powered classrooms. Since the application of AI technologies in education is still new,

teachers, according to [23], should have collaborative learning. They should share their experiences, best practices, challenges, and lesson plans that incorporate AI.

Curriculum issues regarding the integration of AI in education should be equally addressed. Teachers should learn how to develop AI-infused lesson plans. Lesson plans that seamlessly integrate AI, focusing on and ensuring that everything is in alignment with the learning objectives. Preparing teachers for the integration of AI in their job should involve educating them on subject-specific AI applications [21]. Educating them on AI applications relevant to specific subjects, such as language processing for English or AI tools for learning sciences or mathematics, will go a long way to improve effective utilization of AI tools. To foster a more holistic understanding, teachers should have a good knowledge of the interdisciplinary connections of AI across various subjects and explore this potential from time to time.

Teachers also need technical and infrastructural support for effective integration of AI into education service delivery. According to [22], teachers need to have access to AI tools/platforms and resources such as Gen AI, Learning Management System (LMS), educational software, and AI-powered tutoring. Currently, all these are either inadequately supplied or not available in most public secondary schools in Nigeria [15]. It is equally essential to provide dedicated technical support to teachers to address their fears, questions, concerns, and technical problems relating to the new technology.

Change, they say, is constant. Integration of AI in education is an innovation. As such, change management strategies and support should be adopted to assist teachers in adjusting to AI-powered classrooms and also to address teachers' anxiety and resistance to this modern approach. [24] suggested that less experienced teachers should be paired with well-experienced ones who can provide guidance, support, and feedback. It is appropriate to employ continuous evaluation and improvement, which should be based on frequent monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of AI integration, and the collection of feedback from teachers, students, and parents.

This study is anchored on Diffusions of Innovation (DOI) theory and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) theory. The Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory was postulated by Everett Rogers, an American Sociologist, in 1962. The theory explains how new ideas and technologies spread and are adopted. Rogers identified five main elements that influence the spread of a new idea. These are the innovation itself, those adopting it (adopter), communication channels, time, and the social system. These factors can inform the study of AI adoption in education and the factors influencing teachers' decisions to adopt AI-powered tools in their schools; hence, this theory is considered relevant to this study.

The second theory is the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) theory. This theory was postulated by [22]. The theory explained the intersection between technology, pedagogy, and content for the effective integration of AI technology into teaching. This theory emphasizes the importance of teachers' knowledge in these three main areas: content, pedagogy, and technology, and how these areas interact to inform a more comprehensive understanding of teaching with AI technology. The theory is relevant to this study because it helps us to understand teachers' challenges in integrating AI into their teaching practices.

Statement of the Problem

Integration of digital technologies in education is advancing every day. The recent emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) and its integration into the field of education has opened up a lot of opportunities for teachers and educational institutions. Teachers and students can use AI to do a lot of things. Research studies in developed countries have it that teachers have acknowledged that AI helps to reduce their workload, produce interactive content, improve the writing quality of their materials, support teachers in developing innovative learning experiences, conducting evaluations, designing learning plans, etc.

The benefit of integrating AI into education cannot be overestimated. It allows for a hybrid kind of practice to affect instruction and school management. The effective adoption of AI technology depends heavily on adequate possession of ICT skills, knowledge of how AI works, and the provision of basic infrastructure. These factors are grossly inadequate among teachers and many schools in Nigeria. Thus, making the adoption of AI in our educational system very challenging. Many teachers appear not prepared for this innovation and do not even know where and how AI can be integrated into educational service delivery.

It is against this backdrop that the researcher is motivated to carry out a study on the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education and teachers' preparation strategies in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims the aim of investigate the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education and teachers' preparation strategies in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. determine ways integration of AI in education can improve learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. ascertaining teachers' preparation strategies for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in this study:

1. In what ways will the integration of AI in education improve learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What are the teachers' preparation strategies for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

H₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of principals and teachers on the ways AI integration in education can be used to improve learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

H₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of principals and teachers on the teachers' preparation strategies for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised all 274 principals and 6,892 teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample of 407 respondents (69 principals and 338 teachers) representing 5% of the population was drawn through a stratified random sampling technique. Data was collected with the aid of a 16-item questionnaire titled, "Integration of Artificial Intelligence in Education and Teachers' Preparation Strategies Questionnaire (IAIETPSQ)". The instrument was validated by two research experts in the field of Educational Management and one in the field of Measurement and Evaluation from Rivers State University. The reliability index of the instrument was 0.83. This was determined by using the Cronbach Alpha method. The researcher, with the help of two research assistants, administered and retrieved the questionnaire. The data collected were analysed. Mean, mean set, and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the z-test was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. A criterion mean of 2.50 was used to agree or disagree on any questionnaire item.

RESULTS

Research Question one: In what ways will the integration of AI in education improve learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

TABLE 1. Weighted Mean, Means Set, and Standard Deviation of the Responses of Principals and Teachers on Ways Integration of AI in Education will Improve Learning Outcomes in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Principals N = 69		Teachers N = 338		Mean set	Remarks
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂		
1	Provision of personalized learning through adaptive assessments and tailored feedback	3.12	0.71	3.14	0.70	3.13	Agree
2	Provision of real-time guidance.	3.00	0.78	3.08	0.74	3.04	Agreed
3	Provision of one-on-one support.	3.08	0.74	3.10	0.73	3.09	Agreed
4	Provision of an interactive learning experience that enhances students' engagement.	3.04	0.76	3.12	0.72	3.08	Agreed
5	Provide an efficient grading system with instant feedback on assignments/quizzes.	3.16	0.69	3.14	0.70	3.15	Agreed
6	AI enhances accessibility and inclusion for all kinds of students.	3.10	0.72	3.04	0.77	3.07	Agree
7	AI has taken over the position of teachers in the classroom.	2.36	0.80	2.40	0.82	2.38	Disagreed
8	AI can predict students' performance, thus enabling teachers to intervene early and provide necessary support.	3.06	0.75	3.02	0.76	3.04	Agreed
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	2.99	0.74	3.01	0.74		

Table 1 showed that all the items had mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, except item 7, which had a mean score below 2.50. All the items with mean scores that were higher than 2.50 were accepted or agreed on by the respondents, while item 7 was disagreed on by the respondents.

Data analysed in table 1 revealed that ways AI integration in education can improve learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State include: provision of personalized learning; provision of real-time guidance; provision of one-on-one support; provision of interactive learning experience; provision of efficient grading system; enhancing of accessibility and inclusion for all kinds of students; and prediction of students performance for timely intervention and necessary support by the teacher.

Research Question Two: What are the teachers' preparation strategies for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

TABLE 2. Weighted Mean, Means Set, and Standard Deviation of the Responses of Principals and Teachers, on the Teachers' Preparation Strategies for Effective Integration of AI in Education in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Principals N = 69		Teachers N = 338		Mean set	Remarks
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂		
1	Provision of AI literacy for teachers.	3.42	0.59	3.36	0.63	3.39	Agree
2	Offering hands-on training on AI-powered tools/resources.	3.40	0.60	3.38	0.61	3.39	Agreed
3	Teachers should be taught how to infuse AI in their lesson plans.	3.36	0.62	3.32	0.65	3.34	Agreed
4	Teachers should be giving adequate technical support.	3.30	0.66	3.26	0.68	3.28	Agreed
5	Teachers should have access to AI-powered resources.	3.34	0.63	3.34	0.64	3.34	Agreed
6	Teachers should be encouraged to share their experiences on the incorporation of AI in their lessons.	3.32	0.64	3.28	0.67	3.30	Agree
7	Change/innovation management strategies should be adopted in the integration of AI in education.	3.38	0.61	3.40	0.60	3.39	Agreed
8	Teachers should be encouraged to ignore AI technology and its application in education.	2.24	0.69	2.20	0.70	2.22	Disagreed
	Aggregate means and standard deviation.	3.22	0.63	3.19	0.65		

Table 2 revealed that items 1 to 7 had mean scores that were greater than the criterion mean of 2.50 and were accepted as the teachers' preparation strategies for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. On the other hand, item 8 had a mean score that was less than the criterion mean and was rejected by the respondents as part of the teachers' preparation strategies for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Data analysed in table 2 indicated that the teachers' preparation strategies for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State are as follows: provision of AI literacy to teachers; offering hands-on training on AI powered tools, educating teachers on how to infuse AI in their lesson plans; providing adequate technical support for teachers; providing adequate access to AI powered resource; encouraging collaboration among teachers through sharing of experiences; and application of change management strategies in the integration of AI in education.

Test of Hypotheses

The null hypotheses formulated for the study were tested through t-test analysis, which is a test of the difference of means.

H₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of principals and teachers on the ways AI integration in education can be used to improve learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

TABLE 3. Summary of z-Test Analysis of the Mean Scores of Principals and Teachers on Ways AI Integration in Education Can Be Used to Improve Learning Outcomes in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	Level of sign	z-cal	Z- critical	Decision
Principals	69	2.99	0.74	405	0.05	0.205	.. <i>minus</i> .960 \pm 1.960	Not significant
Teachers	338	3.01	0.74					

Data analysed in Table 3 showed that the mean scores of principals and teachers stood at 2.99 and 3.01, respectively. A close look at these mean scores indicated that they are closely related and do not differ so much from each other. Furthermore, at 405 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the calculated z-score of 0.05 is less than the z-table or critical value of ± 1.960 . Hence, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis and therefore upholds that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of principals and teachers on ways AI integration in education can be used to improve learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

H₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of principals and teachers on the teachers' preparation strategies for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in River State.

TABLE 4. Summary of z-Test Analysis of the Mean Scores of Principals and Teachers on Teachers' Preparation Strategies for Effective Integration of AI in Education in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	Level of sign	z-cal	Z- critical	Decision
Principals	69	3.22	0.63	405	0.05	0.359	.. <i>minus</i> .960 \pm 1.960	Not significant
Teachers	338	3.19	0.65					

Data analysed in Table 4 showed that the mean scores of principals and teachers stood at 3.22 and 3.19, respectively. A close examination of these mean scores showed that they are very close and do not differ so much. Furthermore, at 405 degrees of freedom and 0.05 level of significance, the calculated z-score of

0.359 is by far less than the z-table or critical value of ± 1.960 . Hence, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis and therefore upheld that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of principals and teachers on teachers' preparation strategies for effective integrations of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in River State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that ways AI integration in education can improve learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State include: provision of personalized learning, real-time guidance, one-on-one support provision of interactive learning experience. AI helps to personalize learning in various ways. It helps to create a better professional environment for teachers to work more with students with difficulties. It provides learning opportunities for everybody; marginalized people and communities with people with disabilities, refugees, those out of school, and those living in isolated communities. For instance, the use of telepresence robotics allows students with special needs to attend schools at home or hospital, or maintain continuity of learning in emergencies or crises. AI provides one-on-one support and an interactive learning experience to students. These findings are supported by [5], [11], and [17]. AI is very effective in individually directed learning and provides students with choices of where and when they wish to study.

It was also found by this study that AI can provide an efficient grading system, real-time guidance, predict students' performance, and increase access to and inclusive education. AI is an assessment tool, and it can be used to grade multiple-choice tests and essays efficiently. AI provides real-time guidance to the students. It can help map each student's individual learning plans, noting their strengths and weaknesses, and providing adequate support to them. These findings are supported by [12], as well as [13]. AI promotes accessibility and inclusion in education through various adaptive learning platforms, which consider the learning needs of the students, their learning abilities, and styles. AI-powered platforms adjust the difficulty level and lesson contents to suit every student. It equally helps students to focus on areas where they need improvement. AI-powered systems can be used to reach a larger audience, thus making education more accessible and inclusive.

The findings of the study also revealed that teachers' preparation strategies for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State include: provision of AI literacy, offering hands-on-training on AI power resources, educating teachers on how to infuse AI in their lesson plans, providing adequate technical support, providing adequate access to AI powered resources, encouraging collaboration among teachers, and application of change/innovation management strategies. These findings are supported by [14], [23], [20]. Most teachers in senior secondary schools in Rivers State need skills upgrade on AI and how it works. They need proper education on AI, types, and ways of integrating them into classroom activities.

Teachers also require technical support and proper training on how to use AI appropriately. This training should be practical-oriented with AI-powered resources. This will enable them to understand the capabilities and limitations of AI and the strategies they can adopt to effectively integrate it into their teaching practices. Effective and efficient integration of AI in education cannot be possible without teachers having access to AI-powered resources. Computers and ICT tools are grossly inadequate in many public senior secondary schools in Nigeria. Power supply is a serious challenge to the adoption of modern technologies in education in Nigeria and Rivers State in particular. Consideration should therefore be given to adequate provision of infrastructure in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Teachers should be encouraged to collaborate among themselves and share their views and experiences on the utilization of AI. Experienced teachers need to mentor the less experienced ones. In this case, teachers, according to [23], should have collaborative learning, share their experiences, best practices, challenges, and lesson plans that incorporate AI. The integration of AI into teaching and learning is still new in our schools. School administrators need to adopt change/innovation management strategies to gradually change the present behavioural patterns of teachers on AI.

CONCLUSION

The emergence of artificial intelligence in education is attracting so much attention from researchers. This study investigated the integration of AI in education and teachers' preparation strategies in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study has revealed ways AI could be used to improve students' learning outcomes and the strategies that could be adopted to prepare teachers for effective integration of AI in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The researchers therefore concluded that AI technology has so much benefits and it is very useful for improving students' learning outcomes and teachers' effectiveness. Teachers should be adequately prepared and supported for effective integration of AI technology in education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. A comprehensive AI literacy workshop should be organized for teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. The curriculum of teachers' training institutions should be reviewed, and AI courses should be introduced.

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